

Application of Artificial Intelligence for Predicting Stellar Flares: Analysis and Implementation of Transformers

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Flares are energetic eruptions of stars that can negatively affect orbiting planets and the atmospheres of exoplanets. Researching these flares is important for understanding their effects on the habitability of distant worlds. With the advent of exoplanets and their research, the need to predict flares has increased. This encourages the deployment of advanced machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms for the prediction of flares, or to compare of these approaches with classical approaches. New methods make it possible to identify flares from astronomical data with high accuracy. This article managed to analyze the available data suitable for flare prediction, evaluate current approaches from the field of artificial intelligence and select models containing Transformers for flare prediction. The advantage of using models from the Transformer area is the possibility of training in broader data contexts. The article provides interesting results that can be followed up with further research.

1 Introduction

Flares are energetic eruptions that occur in almost all types of stars. Their research has expanded since the advent of exoplanets, for the reason that they can have strong and negative effects on orbiting planets, but also on the atmospheres of exoplanets, for example Mars, because of its missing magnetic field, solar storms directly hit the surface and influence possible life there. When intense, flares can trigger geomagnetic storms that cause technological problems and affect power grids on Earth, but also satellites can be severely damaged [1]. According to [2], these phenomena can dramatically interfere with the chemical balance of atmospheres, which has major implications for the potential habitability of planets. Since the emergence of the importance of exoplanets, the research of these flares has become increasingly important, as it is necessary to understand how flares can affect the habitability and atmospheric conditions on distant worlds. This interest has stimulated the development of new technological approaches, especially the use of

advanced machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms, which can contribute to better prediction and analysis of these dynamic phenomena.

A study by [3] emphasizes the importance of these technologies for the identification and monitoring of extreme solar eruptions that can threaten entire planetary systems [4]. Thanks to modern methods, we can now identify flares from astronomical data with an accuracy previously unattainable. This article focuses on the use of artificial intelligence to analyze data potentially for use in flare prediction, and the design of a flare prediction procedure.

1. It examines the available data (datasets), with different descriptive data (different source data),
2. evaluates the approaches applied so far
3. and describes the possibilities in the field of deployment of language models for the detection of flares (recognition of patterns in light curves, prediction of atmospheric eruptions), while this is important with regard to their potential impacts on the environment of individual exoplanets.

As [5] point out, this accessibility of big data and the development of new analytical tools allow for a more detailed understanding of the dynamics and impacts of starbursts [1, 4]. Research by [1], [4] and [6] has focused on how flares can be predicted and what data can be used.

2 Related works

[1] focused on the use of a machine learning algorithm to identify flares in light curves, applying this to the flaring star TRAPPIST-1, which hosts a planetary system and the rotating variable star KIC 1722506, but they also point out that there is no single way to detect all eruptions because they are very diverse. [4] also looked at flares and the use of artificial intelligence, but their scope was limited to solar flares only.

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This team succeeded in developing a computational method that can predict emission flares by identifying flare precursors and reconstruct eruptive events. For the prediction, the team used convolutional neural networks and long-short term memory, the input data were videos of the Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI) which is a part of the NASA Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO). [1] classified flares using light curves, this paper was of great benefit mainly because it is impossible to identify flares manually even with a large number of observations.

There are now three methods used to predict flares, the first method is empirical prediction, the second is statistical prediction, and the third is numerical simulation. However, it is also possible to apply machine learning methods that show good results.

- Statistical models: These models use historical data to make statistical predictions about the probability and timing of flares. One example is regression analysis, which models the relationships between various variables and flare intensity. These models make it possible to process large amounts of data and provide quick results [7].
- Physical models: Physical models try to simulate the physical processes that lead to the occurrence of flares. These models use basic physical laws, from the fields of magnetohydrodynamics and plasma physics, to generate predictions about the behavior of flares. These models are particularly useful for understanding the conditions leading to flares and for developing strategies to monitor them [8].
- Machine learning models: With the development of artificial intelligence technologies, machine learning models such as neural networks and machine learning methods are increasingly used to predict flares. These models can identify complex patterns and relationships in data that are difficult for human analysts to discern. Machine learning makes it possible to create prediction models with a high degree of accuracy and adaptability to newly acquired data [9].

Machine learning methods have brought considerable progress to the field of flare prediction. However, for a long time, there was no application that could provide real-time space weather forecast information [6]. This changed with the development of an application by [10], who developed their application for predicting flares. Similarly, an application for predicting eruptions was developed by [4]. Both teams used artificial intelligence methods. [10], unlike [4], which

divides magnetogram images into three groups, only divides the images into \geq M-class and $<$ M-class or \geq C-class and $<$ C- class.

Among the eruptions, the most significant are eruptions of class M and higher, due to the fact that eruptions are divided according to X-ray emissions into 5 groups (A, B, C, M and X). Therefore, eruptions of class M and above can have a large effect on the Earth, for example, eruptions of class M can cause short radio interruptions and radiation storms [11]. Therefore, it is good to focus on the type of eruption that could occur within the forecast.

The resulting software from [10] provides the probabilities of flares for the two categories previously mentioned and the maximum class of flares that will occur in the next 24 hours. The advantage of the software from [10] is that it directly downloads images that detect flares and then evaluates them. [4] implemented a Recurrent-Convolutional Network for the prediction of flares long-term. [10] also used an exact feedforward neural network to implement their deep neural network software [6].

[11] focused on comparing machine learning methods for predicting flares of class higher than M, specifically comparing the algorithms: Support Vector Machine [12], Random Forest [13], Light Gradient Boosting Machine [14], these models then also combined with each other, when they used the connectors and and or, and indicated that if two models labeled evaluates the event as positive, then it is positive or characterized that if at least one model marks the event as positive, then it is positive.

When comparing the algorithms themselves, Random Forest achieved the most satisfactory results, overall the best results were achieved by the combination of Support Vector Machine and Random Forest with the conjunction or, so it was when predicting in a 24-hour horizon and for prediction in a 48-hour horizon, the best results were achieved by the algorithm containing Random Forest, specifically in combination with Light Gradient Boosting Machine with the and clutch, Rand Forest alone achieved the best results in a 72-hour horizon. As you can see, each author team approaches the prediction of flares differently within artificial intelligence methods.

However, a method that no author has used for flares prediction, as far as we know, is the use of Transformer technology [15] for prediction, which consists of two parts, namely the decoder and encoder part and is primarily designed for natural language processing tasks. However, due to the perception of context in a broader context, it has been used also for time series prediction. For time series prediction, Transformer was used in their research by, for example, [16], who created ETSformer. It is an architecture that includes

also an encoder and a decoder. In each layer, the encoder removes the seasonal and growth components that enter the decoder and are used for further generation. The ETSformer model achieved very good results for [16], but they point out that they used exponential smoothing attention instead of classical attention in Transformer, because smoothing showed better results. However, [17] point out that the Transformer architecture performs well for natural language processing tasks, but not for time series forecasting, noting that Transformer fails to capture data bias. However, [16] managed to solve this with an exponential smoothing mechanism. [18] have also dealt with a time series forecasting model containing Transformer, who highlight in their model that by using Transformer, the model can learn broad dependencies.

3 Data

Available datasets: The study of flares uses a wide range of datasets, which include both optical and other electromagnetic data acquired from various observation platforms. One of the primary sources is the light curves from the Kepler space telescope, which are publicly available through the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST) and which provide data on the intensity of starlight over time and enable the detection of anomalies including flares [19]. Another important source is the TESS space telescope, whose data are also available at MAST and which are crucial for the continued monitoring of nearby stars in search of flares [20]. There is even a developed convolutional network method for classifying flares at MAST. Regarding solar flares, the SOHO space observatory provides valuable data sets accessible through the SOHO Science Archive that include a broad spectrum of electromagnetic radiation capturing solar activity [21].

In addition to these data from telescopes, spectroscopic data are also important to help identify the chemical and physical characteristics of stellar atmospheres during eruptions. These datasets can be obtained from various spectrographs installed at ground-based and space-based observatories, such as the Hubble Space Telescope, whose spectroscopic archives are also available through MAST [22].

Furthermore, from Klepler data, [23] found a dependence between flare rate, spectral type and quiescent levels of variability in K and M dwarfs. This finding may also serve as an indication during prediction.

To train a model for forecasting, it is good to use data where flares have already been classified and look at the previous course before flares occurred. Most of flares datasets, however, only contain information about the beginning, peak and end of flares, and

possibly their intensity, primarily because flares are by their very nature a random release of energy in the stellar corona, and flares can occur before the flares themselves magnetic activity, but this does not necessarily mean that flares will occur. For this reason, it is important to study a wide range of properties such as the star’s magnetic field or the behavior of the coronal structure for their prediction.

4 Metrics

The MAE (Mean absolute error) and MSE (Mean Squared Error) metrics will subsequently be used to evaluate the forecast, or RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error), which take into account the number of prediction n and the magnitude of the error e , see for details [24].

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |e_i|$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2}$$

$$RMSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2$$

5 Methods

Considering that for the prediction of flares it is necessary to take a large spectrum of properties, it is not a prediction in the classical sense of the word, as is the case, for example, with the weather, which is predicted on the basis of the previous course. In each layer, the encoder removes the seasonal and growth components that enter the decoder and are used for further generation. [25]. Both positive and negative samples are required for flare prediction. Positive samples mean that there will be a flare-up, while negative samples will not. Only large flares (in class M or C) will be considered. For this reason, data classification will be performed first, using the convolutional network from [26]. Thanks to this step, the training dataset from [27] will be able to be expanded as needed, e.g. with SDO data. The latter uses light curves from the MAST bank data for flare detection. Although these data do not contain information about the type of the star, they nevertheless provide a relatively long observation.

For the actual training of the model for prediction, the complete time series will be provided. For these purposes, the ETSformer model from [16] will be used, this model will be used for the reason that it provides

Figure 1: Light curve dataset sample. [27]

relatively good results. Although ETSformer contains Transformers technology, which is primarily intended for natural language processing tasks, the potential of using this technology with stylish modifications is also evident for other artificial intelligence tasks. The evaluation of the success of the model will be carried out with the help of the above mentioned metrics, specifically with the help of the MAE and MSE metrics, the RMSE metric will not be used because its values can be calculated from the MSE values.

6 Results

In [26], the authors take the original time series from [28], here light curves with a cadence of two minutes measured over 27 days as output of the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) mission, and divide them into sequences of 200 cadences (measurements) by centering the data and separating them into flare and non-flare events. Based on this data, it learns a neural network model called Stella (convolutional neural network, teacher learning mode). The dataset contains 5389 manually identified flares and 17,684 non-flare instances. Furthermore, this dataset was split into training, test and validation data in an 80/10/10 ratio.

In this paper, the original light curve data from [28] are used to learn the ETSformer model of [16] so that future light curve states can be predicted using the model. This approach is intended to help predict the occurrence of flares using the generation of additional time series values with their subsequent classification

(flares, non flares). The stella neural network model by [26] was then used to actually classify the predicted data as to whether they were flares or non flares. It is thus a hybrid model combining prediction of future state (flares) and their classification. This can be used with respect to avoiding the influence of flares, with forward knowledge of their occurrence. A substantial part is then associated with the verification of the model thus built (first-pass approach). In the next phase of research, more approaches from the transformer domain for time series prediction can be considered, for example the Informer model [29], or the Autoformer [30]. Subsequently, the different models can be compared using MSE and MAE.

7 Discussion

The use of a model with Transformer brings considerable advantages compared to classic methods for predicting time series, primarily in that it enables the learning of the model in wider contexts [18]. Compared to classical methods used for prediction within artificial intelligence models, such as neural networks, random forest and others, models containing Transformer bring an advantage mainly in the attention mechanism, which allows seasonality to be extracted [16]. Due to the lack of traditional methods such as recurrent networks, gradient vanishing and exploding problems occur, therefore there is a problem with modeling complex relationships with sequential data [18]. For this reason, the method proposed by us, using the ETSformer model, seems to be a suitable

Figure 2: The ETSformer model is shown on the right a) to predict the future course of the light curves. This model is further linked to the Stella convolutional neural network b), which classifies whether or not flares are present. [16, 27]

choice for predicting flares, which are influenced by a large number of factors. The ETSformer model was chosen mainly because it allows to understand how the seasonality and trend of the forecast affect the data [16] instead of the model by [18], which is also based on the Transformer model, however, on seasonal and trend he did not target the component within the forecasting. When using the Transformer model, the question arises, why not use one of the big language models such as GPT-4 [31] or Llama 3 [32] for prediction, the reason is simple. These large language models only contain a decoder, unlike the already mentioned models from [18] and from [16], and their training was performed on text data, which in itself conditions how the model will be further behave. However, this approach is not one of the usual machine learning techniques for predicting flares [11], however, we expect better results from this approach, mainly thanks to the fact that the method, by using the Transformer, will allow a wider field of properties to be taken into account.

8 Conclusions

In this article, it was possible to propose a solution for predicting flares with the help of a model using Transformer. Furthermore, it was possible to analyze datasets containing information about flares and the gap in research, which is the prediction of flares itself. Current papers mainly deal with the classification of flares, but the prediction itself is not so common any-

more. This is mainly because whether a flare occurs or not is affected by a large number of factors, and some of these factors are unknown.

This article serves as a good basis for future research on flare prediction using artificial intelligence, specifically models containing Transformer. The advantage of this approach is that Transformer enables the training of wider contexts compared to conventional approaches to time series prediction of artificial intelligence models.

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